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San Carlos de Bariloche, 20th September 2018

Hereby I certify that Dr. Julián Atilio Puszek participated from 03/01/2009 to 09/01/2010 in a technological transfer project between CNEA (Comisión Nacional de Energía Atómica) and the private Argentinean company (INVAP S.A.) under the Innovation technology law (J-181). For nuclear energy applications, the transfer of technology to the private Argentinean company (INVAP S.A.) consisted in the synthesis of an unknown gadolinium borohydride and the characterization of its physical-chemistry properties. Innovation technology law (J-181).

Yours sincerely,

Dra. Fabiana C. Gennari
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